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PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“FROM GAMEPLAN TO LESSON PLAN”

I grew up in computer shops with CRT monitors
Grayscale keyboard, mouse balls stacked with dirt
Adrenaline is the sound of every tick and click.

Every penny saved in our tiny pockets
Is a minute of pure and non-stop fun and excitement
From counter-terrorist win in Counter-Strike
To godlike victory in Dota 1
One, two more hours and the game is done.

Play DOTA until the break of dawn
Stories untold, memories drawn
These were all part of my game plan.

Life change, so as career
From gamer to teacher, a researcher and an adviser
Experiences before is today's life saver
Now the shops are quiet, friends are out
But the heart of a gamer still burns stout.

For no matter how the years may part
We will always be gamers at heart
From gameplan to lesson plan.

